

BASE EXCHANGE OF MERCURIC IONS ADSORBED ON WOOL.

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In addition to chemical reaction of mercuric chloride with wool in the carrotting process the adsorption of Hg ions have also been established by observations in the base exchange experiments.

While studying the action of $HgCl_2$ solutions of various concentrations in 0.1N-HCl on Merino sheep wool and hair to explain the nature of reactions involved in the mercuric carrotting of wool for increasing the felting power of fibres, Speaksman and Coke (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1939, 35, 246) concluded that at temperatures lower than 40° combination of Hg occurred chiefly with the arginine and lysine side-chains. They also found that deaminated wool had affinity for mercuric chloride and they attribute this either to the presence of nitroso groups and the formation of chelate compounds or to the combination with -NH- groups of the side-chains or of the peptide linkages.

The object of the present work was to examine if chemical combination of $HgCl_2$ with NH_2 and -NH- groups of the body proteins as suggested by Seth (*Biochem. J.*, 1923, 17, 613) can account for the total amount of Hg^{++} ions combined or there was any adsorption occurring simultaneously. Carder and Coffindaffer (*J. Amer. Med. Assoc.*, 1923, 88, 448) have attempted to establish the adsorption of Hg ions on body proteins of dogs from the removal of its poisonous effect by previous intravenous and intraperitoneal injections of NaCl solution. They explain this effect due to the exchange of Hg^{++} ions with Na^+ ions. The authors have performed base exchange experiments with various chlorides and sulphates having mono- and divalent cations, on sheep wool (Sind desert sheep), treated with various solutions of $HgCl_2$ in 0.025N-HCl solutions and established adsorption of Hg^{++} ions in addition to chemical reaction. Various cations tried have been arranged in lyotropic series in accordance with their base-exchange capacities for Hg^{++} ions.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Mercuric chloride solution (0.200M) was prepared in 0.025N-HCl (to avoid hydrolysis) by use of Merck's extra pure mercuric chloride. The wool was washed several times in boiling distilled water, dried in the sun under cover and preserved in $CaCl_2$ desiccator. The mercury was estimated by the gravimetric method, used by Speaksman and Coke (*loc. cit.*) by precipitation as HgS. All experiments were performed in an air thermostat at $35^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$.

It was experimentally found that with the same molality of HgCl_2 but different normality of HCl ($0.025N$ - $0.2N$) the total quantity of Hg^{++} ions taken up 1 g. of wool decreases with the increase in concentration of HCl ; the difference between total Hg taken up in case of $0.2M$ - HgCl_2 in $0.2N$ - and $0.1N$ - HCl respectively is about 68% ; so the least acidity *viz.* $0.025N$ required for avoiding the hydrolysis of HgCl_2 was kept constant in all the experiments.

It was also experimentally found that the maximum amount of Hg^{++} ions adsorbed on 1 g. of wool exchanged with 150 c.c. of $0.2N$ - NaCl ; higher concentrations of NaCl exchange the same quantity of Hg^{++} ions as $0.2N$. So $0.2N$ solutions of the salt were used in all base-exchange experiments.

TABLE I.

Influence of time.

Wool = 1 g. HgCl_2 solution ($0.05M$ in $0.025N$ HCl) = 150 c.c.

Time.	Initial.	Conc. of HgCl_2 .	Final.	Hg taken up by 1g. of wool.
1 hr.	$0.050 M$		$0.0449 M$	0.1511
8	0.050		0.0447	0.1583
16	0.050		0.0446	0.1635
24	0.050		0.0444	0.1684
32	0.050		0.0442	0.1734
40	0.050		0.0441	0.1784

Influence of initial concentrations of HgCl_2 on the adsorbed and reacted quantity was also studied. Wool (1 g.) was immersed in 150 c.c. of HgCl_2 solutions of various concentrations made in $0.025N$ - HCl contained in Jena glass-stoppered bottles for 24 hours in an air thermostat at 35° . The solution was then decanted off and 25 c.c. analysed for Hg^{++} ions. The results are shown in Table II. The wool was washed with cold CO_2 -free distilled water five times, using 30 c.c. at a time. The water was drained out from the wool by pressing it with flat glass rod. The wool was then immersed in 150 c.c. of $0.2N$ - NaCl for 24 hours at 35° , the solution was decanted and 75 c.c. analysed for Hg^{++} ions and the total quantity taken out by NaCl was calculated. Assuming this quantity of Hg^{++} ions to be adsorbed, it was deducted from the total quantity taken up to obtain the quantity reacted. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II.

Initial.	Conc. of HgCl ₂ Final.	Total Hg taken up.	Hg taken out by NaCl.	Hg remaining behind.
0.0250 M	0.0214 M	0.1094 g.	0.0731 g.	0.0363
0.0500	0.0444	0.1684	0.1035	0.0649
0.1000	0.0915	0.2567	0.1649	0.0918
0.1500	0.1373	0.3819	0.2204	0.1615
0.2000	0.1845	0.4656	0.2732	0.1924

In order to compare the base-exchange capacities of various cations and anions, wool (1 g.) immersed in 150 c.c. of 0.05M-HgCl₂ solution in 0.025N HCl for 24 hours at 35°. was washed and treated with 150 c.c. of 0.1N- and 0.2N solutions of various salts for 24 hours at 35° and the exchanged quantity of Hg⁺⁺ ions determined in the same manner as shown above. The results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III.

Total Hg before treatment = 0.1684 g.

Salt used.	Hg exchanged		Hg remaining	
	0.1N.	0.2N.	0.1N.	0.2N.
KCl	0.0893 g.	0.1066 g.	0.0791	0.0618
NH ₄ Cl	0.0863	0.1045	0.0801	0.0639
NaCl	0.0862	0.1035	0.0822	0.0649
CaCl ₂	0.0946	0.1045	0.0738	0.0639
BaCl ₂	0.0931	0.1032	0.0753	0.0652
MgCl ₂	0.0879	0.0966	0.0805	0.0718
K ₂ SO ₄	0.1181	0.1181	0.0503	0.0503
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	0.1164	0.1164	0.0520	0.0520
Na ₂ SO ₄	0.1121	0.1121	0.0563	0.0563
MgSO ₄	0.1131	0.1131	0.0553	0.0553

DISCUSSION.

Table I shows that the total quantity of Hg taken up by 1 g. of wool at first increases quickly and after 1 hour slowly and regularly with time; this proves that there is a chemical reaction between HgCl₂ and wool, because the velocity of adsorption is very great in view of the time intervals;

for the experiments in case of a true solution Lenard (*Sitzungsber. Dent. Akad. Heidelberg*, 1914, 5A, 28) assumes a period of $1/100$ second to 1 second for the setting of equilibrium up to 95%.

From Table II it appears that there is diversion at equilibrium concentration corresponding to $0.1M$ initial concentration of $HgCl_2$ both in the cases of total Hg taken up and the Hg remaining behind after treatment with $0.02N-NaCl$, but there is no such break in case of the curve for Hg^{++} taken out by $NaCl$; this shows that there is adsorption of Hg^{++} ions in addition to the reaction of Hg^{++} ions with wool. The adsorption curve is not a regular parabola, since on plotting $\log x/m$ against $\log c$, it was found that a straight line is not obtained. On the assumption of the reaction of Hg^{++} (remaining behind) with the wool, the reaction curve, obtained by plotting this against equilibrium concentration of $HgCl_2$, shows that there are two types of reactions as concluded by Speakman and Ccke (*loc. cit.*).

Table III shows that the cations of the same valency possess different base-exchange capacities for Hg^{++} ions adsorbed on wool and follow the order $K > NH_4 > Na$ in case of monovalent ions and $Ca > Ba > Mg$ in case of divalent ions. Compared amongst themselves the order followed by cations is $K > NH_4 > Ca > Na > Ba > Mg$ in case of chlorides and $K > NH_4 > Mg > Na$ in case of sulphates. If the sulphates and chlorides with the same cations are compared it is found that sulphates have more base-exchange capacity than chlorides.

The above observations definitely lead to the conclusion that there is adsorption of Hg ions on wool in addition to chemical reactions of $HgCl_2$.

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